

Quantifying Structural Similarity between Indus and Tibetan–Yi Scripts Using Hybrid Vision Embeddings

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Abstract

This study applies a hybrid convolutional–transformer architecture to investigate potential historical connections between the visual morphology of the Indus Valley script and pictographic systems of the Tibetan–Yi Corridor. Using an ensemble of fifteen independently trained models across three target scripts, the analysis finds that, at the glyph level, Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC) corpora are substantially more similar to the Indus corpus (mean cosine similarity = 0.635) than to Proto-Cuneiform (0.102) or Proto-Elamite (0.078), corresponding to a $\sim 6.22\times$ and $8.14\times$ increase, respectively.

Two complementary tests support this pattern. When TYC corpora are compared to candidate source traditions, their nearest neighbor is the Indus corpus rather than either West Asian signary. The converse holds in the Indus-trained embedding space: the Indus script maps more closely to Tibetan–Yi Corridor scripts (mean cosine similarity = 0.930, CI [0.917–0.942]) than to contemporaneous West Asian signaries (0.887 [0.863–0.911] and 0.855 [0.818–0.891]) despite their geographic proximity and well-documented trade. Across dimensionality reduction and clustering procedures, the Indus script consistently clusters nearest to Tibetan–Yi systems.

These computational outcomes correspond with qualitative parallels in numeral formation, gender markers, and iconographic motifs, and are compatible with archaeological evidence for sustained exchange along the ancient Shu–Shendu corridor during the Indus Civilization’s decline. While alternative explanations are still to be explored, the specificity and persistence of these cross-script similarities challenge narratives of isolated script evolution and suggest a more intricate network of visual and cultural transmission linking South and East Asia during the Bronze Age. **Keywords:** Indus Valley Civilization; Tibetan–Yi Corridor; Dongba script; computational archaeology; computer vision; visual embeddings; cultural transmission

1 Introduction

The endurance of language and script across millennia crystallizes human memory and exchange. Few enigmas embody this resilience more than the undeciphered script of the Indus Valley Civilization (IVC, c. 2600–1900 BCE). Despite its contemporaneity with Sumerian cuneiform and Egyptian hieroglyphs, the Indus script remains unreadable: 419 known signs scattered across 2,290 artifacts [27]. Debate over its linguistic lineage (Proto-Dravidian, Austroasiatic, Indo-Aryan, or Proto-Cuneiform/Proto-Elamite [West Asian]) has spanned a century, yet whether visual and symbolic elements of the Indus script diffused eastward, surviving within the pictographic traditions of the Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC), remains scarcely explored.

Situated along the eastern edge of the Tibetan Plateau, the TYC historically bridged South and East Asia and hosts one of the world’s densest clusters of Tibeto-Burman languages and symbolic systems [30]. Among them, the Naxi *Dongba* script, often described as the world’s last living pictographic writing system, exhibits visual features that, in this study, appear structurally comparable to certain Indus signs, particularly in numerical notation, gender markers, and cosmological motifs. While Dongba shares general pictographic features with many ancient sign systems, this study examines whether its structural affinities with the Indus corpus are comparatively stronger.

The Indus–Tibetan–Yi comparison is not proposed as a direct line of descent but as a testable possibility within broader late Neolithic and Bronze Age exchange systems linking South Asia to the eastern Himalayan and Hengduan regions. Archaeological and genetic evidence suggests that the Tibetan–Yi Corridor functioned less as a barrier than as a highland conduit, connecting Northeast India, Yunnan, and Sichuan through multi-stage interaction zones [22, 30]. These zones were mediated by upland intermediaries rather than continuous state-level contact. Sustained interaction along the early trans-Hengduan Shu–Shendu route (Figure 1) provides a plausible context for such exchanges [22]. Cowrie shells from the Indian Ocean, hybrid rice strains, and shared bronze typologies at *Sanxingdui* and *Jinsha* attest to Indo-Tibetan interaction by the second millennium BCE [11, 13]. Within such networks, durable cultural forms, including prestige goods, crop packages, metallurgical knowledge, and visual conventions, could circulate across considerable distances without requiring mass migration or linguistic replacement. Non-Sinitic pictographic traditions in the region (Dongba in Yunnan, Ba–Shu symbols in Sichuan, and early Yi manuscripts in Liangshan) may therefore represent regional continuations of a broader Bronze Age graphic repertoire whose structural features can be evaluated computationally.

Figure 1: Proposed exchange routes linking South Asia and the Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC), including the Shu–Shendu corridor and associated archaeological evidence [22].

A central difficulty in evaluating any potential relationship between the Indus script and pictographic traditions of the Tibetan–Yi Corridor is the temporal distance between the primary Indus corpus (third–second millennium BCE) and the earliest securely dated Dongba manuscripts (first millennium CE onward), as seen in Figure 2. Rather than treating this interval as grounds for dismissal, the chronological gap is treated here as an empirical condition: if elements of a transmitted or shared visual convention persisted across intermediary highland traditions (including Ba–Shu/Sanxingdui inscriptions, pre-Buddhist Tibetan rock art traditions [Appendix A.9], and related corridor pictographies), they should leave a measurable structural signal at the script level that can be evaluated relative to similarities observed between the Indus script and other contemporaneous pictographic systems, as well as between the TYC corpora and said systems.

Figure 2: Approximate temporal ranges of the script traditions considered [8]. The gap between the Indus corpus and later Tibetan–Yi Corridor pictographic systems motivates a test of persistent visual conventions rather than assumptions of continuous textual transmission.

This paper represents, to the author’s knowledge, the first computational evaluation

of structural relationships between the Indus script and Tibetan–Yi Corridor sign systems through an integrated archaeological and computational framework. While previous scholarship has examined Indus connections westward or treated Tibetan–Yi traditions within regional contexts, no prior study has directly compared these corpora within a unified trans-Asian analysis. Using computer-vision-based embeddings to operationalize cross-script affinity as a reproducible measurement, the study establishes a quantitative basis for assessing relative morphological similarity among undeciphered signaries. These results are interpreted as indicators of structural affinity rather than linguistic or genealogical descent. Because pictographic systems may share motifs without sharing language, the analysis evaluates whether Tibetan–Yi Corridor scripts exhibit stronger structural similarity to the Indus corpus than to other contemporaneous sign systems within the same comparative framework. The reciprocal test, whether the Indus corpus is in turn nearer to TYC than to West Asian signaries within Indus-trained embeddings, is reported as a complementary, stronger form of the same comparison. In this framing, the chronological gap functions as a falsifiable constraint: if visual conventions were intermittently mediated across plateau and corridor traditions, they should still register as a consistent script-level morphological signal even without continuous textual transmission.

1.1 Hypotheses

H₁: Indus–Tibetan–Yi Structural Affinity

If visual conventions circulated across trans-Himalayan exchange networks, Indus and Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC) signaries should exhibit their strongest structural similarity to one another relative to other contemporaneous sign systems.

Prediction: Embedding similarity, clustering, and dimensionality reduction analyses will position TYC corpora closest to the Indus corpus, and the Indus corpus closest to TYC corpora, relative to Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite.

H₂: Alternative West Asian Transmission

If similarities instead reflect broader diffusion of West Asian graphic conventions, Tibetan–Yi Corridor scripts should exhibit stronger structural similarity to Proto-Cuneiform or Proto-Elamite than to the Indus corpus.

Prediction: Embedding and clustering analyses will position TYC corpora nearer to West Asian sign systems than to the Indus corpus.

If neither prediction is supported, observed similarities are most parsimoniously explained by independent pictographic convergence.

1.2 Objectives and Scope

1. Establish archaeological and ethnographic plausibility for contact between the IVC and TYC regions through trade-route and cultural evidence.
2. Introduce a hybrid CNN–Transformer framework for morphological comparison across Indus, West Asian, and TYC signaries.
3. Interpret computational outcomes within an anthropological model of early Asian symbol exchange.

This study does not attempt decipherment but tests for statistically significant morphological correspondence, reframing an enduring archaeological mystery within a connected trans-Asian landscape where ideas, materials, and symbols traveled farther than language itself.

2 Methodology

2.1 Dataset Composition

The dataset includes three target ancient scripts and three comparison datasets, emphasizing visual structure (complete acquisition details appear in Appendix A.1; a full list of software packages and implementation libraries is provided in Appendix A.2). The target scripts are the Indus Valley script, Proto-Cuneiform, and Proto-Elamite, representing potential source traditions for influence on the Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC). For comparison, three Tibetan–Yi Corridor script corpora were assembled: Old Dongba (manuscript-derived glyphs), Modern Dongba (standardized font-rendered glyph set¹), and the ancient TYC composite (Old Dongba, Ba–Shu/Sanxingdui glyphs, and Classical Yi script in equal parts, balanced via augmentation). This structure enables a controlled comparison: do TYC scripts share more visual commonality with Indus signaries than with West Asian systems? Frequency was not used as a filtering criterion, as hapax legomena are typical in low-resource corpora and still represent cumulative stylistic tradition [12, 26]. Table 1 reports the number of glyph images per corpus after preprocessing. Training-time augmentation is applied on-the-fly (Section 2.2) and does not expand the on-disk corpus.

Table 1: Number of glyph images per corpus prior to training-time augmentation.

Corpus	Images	Notes
Indus	716	seal and inscription glyph crops
Proto-Cuneiform	2089	tablet sign extractions
Proto-Elamite	1510	tablet sign extractions
TYC composite	8766	Ba–Shu, Classical Yi, Old Dongba balanced
Modern Dongba	2121	standardized Modern Dongba set
Old Dongba	2380	manuscript-derived glyphs

Terminology note Terminology is standardized as follows:

- **Old Dongba** refers to pre-standardized manuscript forms.
- **Modern Dongba** refers to standardized twentieth-century forms.
- **TYC** denotes the combined dataset of Ba–Shu, Classical Yi, and Old Dongba.

Note on figure labels: Figures generated by the analysis pipeline use the legacy dataset codes *Naxi-Dongba* and *Old-Naxi*, which correspond to *Modern Dongba* and *Old Dongba* respectively. The descriptive names are used throughout the prose, and these codes appear only as labels within figure legends.

2.2 Data Preprocessing

All images were standardized to 224×224 pixels (the input size for both Swin Transformer and ResNet architectures), using a custom SquarePad and resize transform while preserving aspect ratio. Images were converted to grayscale, replicated across three channels to match ImageNet-pretrained backbones, and normalized using standard ImageNet statistics (mean=[0.485, 0.456, 0.406], std=[0.229, 0.224, 0.225]). Only the historical Dongba data required additional denoising; color scans were binarized via adaptive thresholding, morphologically closed with a 2×2 kernel, and denoised using Non-Local Means (`fastNlMeansDenoising`) following standard paleographic preprocessing protocols [7].

¹Modern standardized Dongba is Sinicized and formed of Chinese-like strokes. Both datasets were analyzed separately to account for stylistic evolution over time.

Augmentation Techniques To expand the effective dataset and improve model robustness, the `AugmentationPipeline` class applied geometric and photometric transformations while preserving glyph integrity:

1. **Geometric:** Random rotations ($\pm 45^\circ$) [17], scaling (0.85–1.15 \times) [32], translations ($\pm 10\%$), minor affine and elastic deformations.
2. **Visual:** Brightness/contrast adjustments (0.7–1.5 \times), sharpness and blur (0.5–1.2 radius), and random noise injection [16].
3. **Background:** Texture perturbations and color jittering to mimic tablet wear and digitization variance.

For each original image in the target-script training splits, three augmented variants were generated per epoch (yielding four views per image per epoch, including the original). Augmentations were applied on-the-fly via the `AugmentedScriptDataset` class rather than being materialized on disk, so the figures in Table 1 reflect pre-augmentation corpus sizes.

2.3 Model Architecture

Preliminary Swin-only trials (as in [23]) failed to capture fine-grained stroke features across signaries, producing feature collapse. To remedy this, this study introduces a hybrid CNN–Transformer model optimized via self-supervised contrastive learning, combining local detail extraction (ResNet-18) and global relational encoding (Swin Transformer [21]).

Figure 3: ResNet-18–Swin Transformer hybrid encoder used to produce glyph embeddings. Local stroke-level morphology is captured by the CNN pathway while global spatial relationships are encoded by the Transformer; fused representations form the embedding space used for cross-script comparison.

CNN (ResNet-18) Component The CNN encoder extracts hierarchical features through stacked residual blocks (see Appendix A.13, Equation 4). Each 3×3 convolution layer with ReLU activation and batch normalization contributes to a 512-dimensional representation summarizing local curvature, junction, and stroke density, all crucial for ancient glyph morphology.

Transformer (Swin) Component Transformers employ scaled dot-product attention [33] (Appendix A.13, Equation 5). The Swin variant localizes attention to windowed regions, merging patches hierarchically (Figure 4), thus modeling spatial layout efficiently while maintaining global coherence.

Figure 4: Shifted-window attention in the Swin Transformer compared with global attention in standard ViT architectures. Windowed attention preserves spatial locality while maintaining linear computational complexity, which is advantageous for structurally dense glyph images [21].

Feature Fusion CNN (512-d) and Transformer (1024-d) outputs are concatenated into a 1536-d embedding and projected through a two-layer MLP with batch normalization, ReLU activation, and dropout (Appendix A.13, Equation 6), yielding compact, discriminative representations sensitive to both local and structural morphology [1, 3, 14].

2.4 Ensemble Modeling

To reduce variance and enhance reliability, five independent models were trained per target script (15 total), each with randomized initialization following ensemble learning principles [18]. The five models are five independent trainings of the same architecture per target script (different random seeds/minibatch order), not five different architectures. At inference, embeddings are averaged across the five runs (ensemble average). Validation loss and convergence epochs are summarized in Table 2, with full training-curve diagnostics and convergence summaries for all ensemble members provided in Appendix A.12. Averaging embeddings across ensemble members produced consensus features with lower variance and greater generalization than any single model. Leave-one-out tests confirmed ensemble stability.

Table 2: Ensemble training summary showing best validation loss for each model.

Target	Model	Seed	Validation loss	Checkpoint
Proto-Cuneiform	1	42	8.8012	Proto-Cuneiform_ensemble_1
Proto-Cuneiform	2	43	8.7174	Proto-Cuneiform_ensemble_2
Proto-Cuneiform	3	44	8.8193	Proto-Cuneiform_ensemble_3
Proto-Cuneiform	4	45	8.7738	Proto-Cuneiform_ensemble_4
Proto-Cuneiform	5	46	9.2726	Proto-Cuneiform_ensemble_5
Indus	1	42	9.6562	Indus_ensemble_1
Indus	2	43	9.4926	Indus_ensemble_2
Indus	3	44	9.3033	Indus_ensemble_3
Indus	4	45	9.9217	Indus_ensemble_4
Indus	5	46	10.0576	Indus_ensemble_5
Proto-Elamite	1	42	9.4655	Proto-Elamite_ensemble_1
Proto-Elamite	2	43	10.2290	Proto-Elamite_ensemble_2
Proto-Elamite	3	44	9.9595	Proto-Elamite_ensemble_3
Proto-Elamite	4	45	9.3049	Proto-Elamite_ensemble_4
Proto-Elamite	5	46	9.4081	Proto-Elamite_ensemble_5

2.5 Training Objective and Implementation

The objective followed an enhanced NT-Xent contrastive formulation [6]:

$$\mathcal{L} = -\log \frac{\exp(\text{sim}(z_i, z_j)/\tau)}{\sum_{k \neq i} \exp(\text{sim}(z_i, z_k)/\tau)} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{var}} + 0.1 \mathcal{L}_{\text{unif}} \quad (1)$$

where cosine similarity $\text{sim}(z_i, z_j)$ enforces proximity of positive pairs. Variance and uniformity terms prevent feature collapse, distributing embeddings evenly on the hypersphere. Training employed AdamW (lr = 3×10^{-5}) with cosine decay and 10 % warm-up.

For each target script (Indus, Proto-Cuneiform, Proto-Elamite), the target corpus was split into train/val/test partitions (70/20/10), and the encoder was trained self-supervised on the training split, with checkpoints selected by validation loss. The same trained encoder is then used as a fixed feature extractor to embed images from all corpora for cross-script comparison.

All models were trained on an NVIDIA A100 (40 GB VRAM) using PyTorch mixed-precision and gradient clipping (max_norm = 1.0). Warm-up cosine scheduling and adaptive weight decay (1×10^{-3}) stabilized convergence.

2.6 Evaluation and Validation

Pairwise cosine similarity between script embeddings was computed as:

$$\text{sim}(S_1, S_2) = \frac{1}{|S_1||S_2|} \sum_{x \in S_1} \sum_{y \in S_2} \frac{z(x)^T z(y)}{\|z(x)\| \|z(y)\|} \quad (2)$$

Aggregate script-level similarities (Equation 3) complemented glyph-level scores:

$$\text{ScriptSim}(S_1, S_2) = \frac{\bar{z}(S_1)^T \bar{z}(S_2)}{\|\bar{z}(S_1)\| \|\bar{z}(S_2)\|} \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{z}(S) = \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{x \in S} z(x)$ denotes the mean embedding over all glyph images in script corpus S .

Unsupervised clustering (Ward linkage) and dimensionality reduction methods (t-SNE, PCA) revealed stable proximity patterns (e.g., Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite clustering together, and Old Dongba aligning closely with the broader TYC composite; Appendix A.3).

2.7 Statistical Analysis

The hypothesis that TYC scripts exhibit greater similarity to Indus than to West Asian signaries was tested using Welch’s t-tests [34]. Bonferroni-corrected thresholds confirmed robust significance ($p < 0.001$). Leave-out ensemble checks ensured that removing any model did not alter significance, following stability criteria from [10].

2.8 Limitations and Controls

Several constraints are acknowledged including small corpus size, heterogeneous digitization quality, and cross-script complexity. Controls included data augmentation, ensemble averaging, dropout (0.1), early stopping, and Grad-CAM verification on the CNN pathway (Appendix A.8) to confirm that stroke-level morphology (rather than background or padding artifacts) contributed strongly to the learned representations. Swin-side attention interpretability is not reported here because standard visualization methods produced unstable, non-local artifacts in the present setting; interpretability claims are therefore restricted to the CNN pathway, where Grad-CAM provides reliable localization. These precautions make the detected inter-regional affinities both statistically and visually credible.

In sum, this methodological framework integrates deep learning, ensemble variance control, and interpretability tools to extract reproducible visual signatures from ancient scripts, forming the empirical backbone for the results that follow.

3 Results

This section presents a comparative analysis of the Tibetan–Yi Corridor corpora (Modern Dongba, Old Dongba, and the TYC composite) against the target ancient writing systems (Indus, Proto-Cuneiform, and Proto-Elamite) using feature representations generated by the hybrid vision model.²

3.1 Cross-Script Similarity Metrics

Table 3: Mean Cosine Similarity Between Comparison and Target Scripts

Comparison Script	Indus	Proto-Cuneiform	Proto-Elamite
TYC	0.635	0.102	0.078
Modern Dongba	0.634	0.109	0.087
Old Dongba	0.617	0.106	0.076

Table 3 shows that all three comparison scripts (TYC composite, Modern Dongba, Old Dongba) align far more closely with the Indus corpus (mean cosine similarity 0.617–0.635) than with Proto-Cuneiform (0.102–0.109) or Proto-Elamite (0.076–0.087). The roughly sixfold gap directly supports H1: when each TYC corpus is compared to the three target scripts, its nearest neighbor is consistently Indus rather than either West Asian signary. By the same comparison,

²TYC here denotes the composite dataset defined in Section 2.1 (Ba-Shu/Sanxingdui, Classical Yi, and Old Dongba in equal parts); Old Dongba accordingly appears both as a standalone comparison corpus and as a component of TYC.

H2, under which TYC scripts would align more closely with West Asian than with Indus, is not supported.

A complementary test reverses the anchor. Figure 5 reports cosine similarities from the Indus corpus to every other corpus within the Indus-trained embedding space. Here too, the Indus script’s nearest neighbor among the comparison corpora is TYC (mean 0.930) rather than Proto-Cuneiform (0.887) or Proto-Elamite (0.855). Whereas Table 3 establishes that TYC’s closest match is Indus (the H1 prediction), Figure 5 establishes the converse, that Indus’s closest match is TYC, which exceeds H1 as stated. Within the Proto-Cuneiform- and Proto-Elamite-trained spaces, by contrast, those two West Asian corpora show their strongest mutual proximity (Appendix A.11), consistent with their shared regional and chronological context. Additional script-to-script cosine similarity plots across all three trained embedding spaces appear in Appendix A.7.

Figure 5: Script-level similarities to Indus in the Indus-trained embedding space (ensemble mean with variability across seeds). Points show mean cosine similarity between each corpus and the Indus corpus after ensemble averaging.

Direct Script-to-Script Embedding Comparison Table 4 quantifies the converse direction with confidence intervals, using Indus as the anchor.³ Aggregate script embeddings capture higher-order compositional structure beyond individual glyphs.

³That is, the Indus ensemble is used as the feature extractor and all corpora are embedded into this space prior to similarity computation. Equivalent matrices for Proto-Cuneiform-trained and Proto-Elamite-trained embedding spaces are provided in Appendix A.11.

Table 4: Direct Script-to-Script Embedding Similarity

Source Script	Target Script	Mean Similarity	95% CI
Indus	TYC	0.930	[0.917, 0.942]
Indus	Proto-Cuneiform	0.887	[0.863, 0.911]
Indus	Proto-Elamite	0.855	[0.818, 0.892]
Indus	Old Dongba	0.878	[0.829, 0.927]
Indus	Modern Dongba	0.852	[0.836, 0.868]

The Indus–TYC relationship (0.930) exceeds those with Proto-Cuneiform (0.887) and Proto-Elamite (0.855), suggesting a stronger structural affinity. Old Dongba (0.878) aligns more closely than Modern Dongba (0.852), suggesting older forms preserve archaic traits. Higher script-level values (0.85–0.93) relative to glyph-level (0.08–0.64) indicate that aggregate representations capture underlying compositional similarity not apparent in individual signs.

3.2 Ensemble Consistency

Model-by-model results confirm Indus dominance (mean 0.635 vs. 0.102 and 0.078 for West Asian systems). Even the outlier model_4’s elevated Proto-Cuneiform similarity remains far below Indus values, implying model-specific variation, not structural change.

Table 5: Complete Similarity Matrix Across All Models

Comparison Script	Model	Indus	Proto-Cuneiform	Proto-Elamite
TYC	model_0	0.607199	0.064351	0.098311
TYC	model_1	0.613448	0.067255	0.065887
TYC	model_2	0.626782	0.072332	0.081921
TYC	model_3	0.650874	0.073373	0.070953
TYC	model_4	0.678075	0.231436	0.074483
Modern Dongba	model_0	0.577379	0.070971	0.082362
Modern Dongba	model_1	0.655400	0.054296	0.098983
Modern Dongba	model_2	0.578332	0.051874	0.093169
Modern Dongba	model_3	0.684051	0.082636	0.077289
Modern Dongba	model_4	0.675574	0.282917	0.083985
Old Dongba	model_0	0.620153	0.072526	0.101854
Old Dongba	model_1	0.570650	0.076422	0.052467
Old Dongba	model_2	0.653981	0.075445	0.086738
Old Dongba	model_3	0.596160	0.086085	0.071727
Old Dongba	model_4	0.645789	0.220979	0.065582

Full statistical test outputs and additional similarity summaries are provided in Appendix A.10 and Appendix A.11.

3.3 Dimensionality and Clustering

Figure 6: t-SNE projection of corpus embeddings in a target-trained feature space (Proto-Cuneiform-trained encoder shown).

Figure 6 shows t-SNE applied to embeddings computed in the Proto-Cuneiform-trained feature space; equivalent projections for Indus- and Proto-Elamite-trained spaces are provided in Appendix A.3. All three t-SNE projections form three distinct clusters: (1) Proto-Cuneiform/Proto-Elamite, (2) Indus with TYC and Old Dongba, and (3) Modern Dongba, supporting a tripartite structure of West Asian, ancient TYC-IVC, and Sinicized scripts (Figure 6). In conjunction, PCA projections from all three trained spaces (Appendix A.4) reproduce this division, with Modern Dongba as an outlier due to later Sinicization [7–9].

Hierarchical clustering (complete linkage on cosine distance $(1 - \cos)$) yields two macro-clusters: (1) Indus + TYC/Old Dongba and (2) Proto-Cuneiform + Proto-Elamite (Figure 7). Modern Dongba merges later, mirroring its stylistic drift.

Figure 7: Hierarchical clustering of script corpora using cosine distance in the Indus-trained embedding space (complete linkage). Branch structure summarizes relative affinity among corpora under the Indus feature representation.

Supplementary hierarchical clustering results across embedding spaces and linkage criteria are provided in Appendix A.5. Additionally, clustered similarity heatmaps for each embedding space are provided in Appendix A.6.

4 Discussion

4.1 Interpretation and Historical Context

Across 15 models and multiple analyses, glyph-level similarities show that TYC corpora exhibit $\sim 6\times$ higher similarity to Indus (mean 0.635) than to West Asian systems (0.102–0.109). Direct script embeddings (Indus–TYC 0.930) strengthen this case, showing closer alignment than with Proto-Cuneiform (0.887) or Proto-Elamite (0.855). Despite known Indus–Mesopotamian contact, the visual data suggest a parallel or eastward channel of cultural exchange, perhaps along the Shu–Shendu corridor. Modern Dongba’s divergence, consistently clustering apart, validates model sensitivity to later Sinicization and supports an older Indus–TYC substrate.

4.2 Methodological Contributions

The hybrid CNN–Transformer architecture integrates convolutional local feature extraction with Transformer global relations, capturing stroke-level and compositional patterns. Combined with ensemble averaging and contrastive loss, it provides reproducible, quantitative morphology maps for undeciphered scripts. This study’s dual glyph- and script-level analysis reveals how fine- and macro-level structures jointly encode cultural transmission.

4.3 Alternative Explanations and Iconographic Parallels

Possible alternatives include (1) independent invention of similar pictography, (2) derivation from an older symbolic ancestor, or (3) convergent evolution under similar visual constraints. Yet the specificity of shared numeral, gender, and sky motifs, coupled with statistical consistency, strengthens the case for direct or indirect cultural transmission.

Numerals Indus stroke numerals (1–9) [12, 26, 36] parallel Dongba’s vertical tally marks (Figure 8). Both employ straight strokes, unlike the wedge marks of West Asia, reflecting adaptation to hard media such as wood or stone. The resemblance persists despite geographic distance, distinguishing both systems from horizontal Chinese numerals [25].

	Four	Five	Seven	Nine
Old				
New				
Indus				

Figure 8: Examples of stroke-based numeral formation across Indus and Dongba traditions. Older Dongba manuscript forms are shown alongside standardized modern variants to illustrate continuity and later stylistic drift.

Gender and Other Motifs Mahadevan’s reading of Indus “jar” and “arrow” signs as gender markers [24] aligns with Dongba’s analogous phallic and triangular forms (Figure 9). Similarly, Indus “roof” and Dongba “sky” modifiers (Figure 10), and triple-triangle “fire” signs shared by Indus, Ba-Shu, and Dongba scripts (Figure 11), suggest recurring semantic correspondences. Such motifs, less prone to arbitrary invention, offer qualitative reinforcement for quantitative affinities.

Indus		
Dongba		
Ba-Shu		

Figure 9: Representative Indus, Dongba, and Ba-Shu forms commonly interpreted as gender or agentive markers. The figure juxtaposes morphologically similar motifs discussed qualitatively alongside the embedding-based similarity analysis.

Indus	
Dongba	
Ba-Shu	

Figure 10: Comparative examples of "roof" or "sky" modifiers across Indus, Dongba, and Ba-Shu materials. Shared compositional placement above primary glyph elements motivates their inclusion as qualitative parallels.

Indus		
Dongba		
Ba-Shu		

Figure 11: Variants of a triple-triangle motif associated with "fire" or related semantic fields across Indus and Tibetan–Yi Corridor traditions. Examples illustrate recurring structural arrangements rather than claims of direct semantic equivalence.

5 Conclusions

This study not only supports the primary hypothesis of stronger Indus–TYC similarity (relative to TYC–West Asian comparisons), but also broadens the comparative landscape of prior Indus–West Asian models by suggesting that Tibetan–Yi Corridor traditions may represent an additional and previously underexplored axis of structural affinity. Through ensemble testing with a hybrid CNN–Transformer architecture, the analysis consistently revealed approximately sixfold higher similarity between TYC scripts and the Indus script (0.635) compared to Proto-Cuneiform (0.102) or Proto-Elamite (0.078) in glyph-level analysis. Direct script-to-script embedding comparison provided the strongest findings, showing an even stronger Indus–TYC connection (0.930) than with Proto-Cuneiform (0.887) or Proto-Elamite (0.855). These results remained robust across five independently trained models and multiple analytical approaches, including cosine similarity, dimensionality reduction, and hierarchical clustering techniques.

Combined with qualitative observations of pictorial parallels in numerals, gender markers, and key iconographic motifs such as the sky/roof and fire symbols, these outcomes suggest that the similarities may be more than coincidental, and instead reflect genuine historical or cultural connections between the Indus Valley and the TYC script traditions.

In conjunction with anthropological and archaeological evidence, these findings lend support to the hypothesis of symbolic transmission along the ancient *Shu–Shendu* road, active during the critical period following the decline of Indus urban centers in the second millennium BCE. Cross-regional exchanges (including Indian Ocean cowrie shells found in southwestern China, crop diffusion, and shared bronze typologies) substantiate the existence of sustained contact networks through which symbolic systems could have traveled.

While independent invention or convergent evolution remain possible explanations, the consistency, specificity, and recurrence of the cross-script correspondences identified through multiple independent computational and anthropological methods make chance alone a less persuasive explanation. The consistent clustering of Indus, Old Dongba, and TYC scripts, together with repeated iconographic affinities, points toward a more direct relationship than previously recognized.

Ultimately, these findings challenge conventional narratives of isolated script development in South and East Asia and invite reconsideration of early trans-Himalayan networks of cultural transmission. By bridging computational paleography and anthropological inquiry, this research introduces new perspectives on Indus cultural interactions and contributes quantitative evidence to the long-standing question of its script’s origins and influence.

5.1 Limitations

Several methodological constraints must be acknowledged. The corpus of images for each script remains limited: only about 5% of the Indus Valley Civilization has been excavated, and extant inscriptions, mostly on seals, reflect narrow functional contexts. Likewise, the Old Dongba dataset is incomplete, as many early *Rerko* manuscripts were destroyed or remain inaccessible, producing a frequency bias. The models capture visual structure rather than phonological or semantic meaning; thus, similarity does not imply linguistic equivalence. Variations in digitization quality, preservation, and contrast across datasets may introduce residual biases, despite preprocessing standardization and Grad-CAM verification. These factors constrain the scope of interpretation and underscore the need for broader, higher-quality corpora.

5.2 Future Research

Building on these results, several promising avenues emerge:

1. Apply the computational framework to the extensive corpus of rock art on the Tibetan Plateau [22], which may reveal further links between TYC morphology and Indus symbolism.
2. Expand archaeological investigation along the *Shu–Shendu* corridor, particularly in Northeast India and the eastern Tibetan Plateau, regions underexplored despite their potential to clarify routes of Bronze Age transmission between the Indus, Sanxingdui, and Jinsha cultures [13].
3. Integrate linguistic or semantic annotations where available into the visual embedding framework, enabling cross-modal comparisons that could advance decipherment efforts for both Indus and Ba–Shu scripts.
4. Extend comparative modeling to additional ancient systems from Central and East Asia to contextualize similarity magnitudes and further map networks of cultural and symbolic exchange.

Such research would refine both the methodological rigor and cultural resolution of computational paleography, helping illuminate the broader narrative of script evolution and interaction across Asia.

5.3 Data, Code, and Materials Availability

All source code and analysis notebooks are available through the project GitHub repository (<https://github.com/oohalakkadi/ivc2tyc>). The complete research archive—including datasets, trained model checkpoints, extracted feature embeddings, and generated experimental outputs—is permanently archived on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20755243>). The preprint version of this article is archived separately on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20018003>).

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A Additional Material

A.1 Data Acquisition

All code, datasets, trained model checkpoints, feature embeddings, and generated outputs used in this study are archived on Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20755243). During development, Google Drive served only as the working storage environment for Google Colab and is retained solely to preserve the original execution paths within the notebooks; it is not the archival source of record.

Indus Dataset The Indus script dataset was retrieved from the *Interactive Corpus of Indus Texts* (ICIT) [35] hosted at <https://www.indus.epigraphica.de/>. The complete HTML corpus was downloaded via authenticated requests and parsed using BeautifulSoup (Appendix A.2). Sign images were extracted from the ICIT site and downloaded programmatically using Python’s requests library (Appendix A.2), authenticated via HTTP Basic Authentication. The dataset includes the full corpus of Indus signs, saved as .jpg images for use in visual similarity analysis.

Proto-Cuneiform Dataset The Proto-Cuneiform dataset was sourced from the [proto-cuneiform_signs](#) GitHub repository maintained by the Cuneiform Digital Library Initiative (CDLI) [5]. The dataset includes .jpg images of Proto-Cuneiform signs located in the archsigns directory. All images are licensed under CC BY, in accordance with Robert K. Englund’s permissions. Files were cloned and extracted for analysis in this project.

Proto-Elamite Dataset The Proto-Elamite dataset was obtained from the pe-decipher-toolkit GitHub repository [29], released in connection with Born et al. [4]. The dataset includes categorized .png images of Proto-Elamite signs from the PE_mainforms and PE_num directories. This resource was developed to support computational decipherment research and accompanies the paper on sign clustering and topic extraction in Proto-Elamite.

Modern Dongba Dataset The Modern Dongba dataset was generated from the BabelStone Naxi LLC font [2], containing 2,162 glyphs derived from Lǐ Lǐncàn’s *Naxi Pictographic Symbols Dictionary* [19]. Glyph images corresponding to Unicode points U+E000 to U+E849 were rendered as .png files at 224×224 resolution using the Python Pillow library (Appendix A.2). This dataset was created specifically for this project to support pictographic analysis.

Old Dongba Dataset The Old Dongba dataset was extracted from the VGTS (Versatile Glyph Text Spotting) GitHub repository [37]. This dataset includes Dongba Buddhist Hieroglyphic manuscripts (DBH), with 3,633 annotated bounding boxes across 253 categories. Glyphs were cropped from annotated manuscripts and additional support images were processed for one-shot learning tasks. Data includes hand-written character samples for training and evaluation.

Classical Yi Dataset The Classical Yi dataset was sourced from the *Ancient Yi Script Handwriting Sample Repository*, published in *Scientific Data* [20]. The dataset includes 427,939 handwritten samples across 2,922 classes, collected from 310 participants. Images were downloaded from the Science Data Bank repository and organized by category. The dataset covers a wide variety of handwriting styles and is used as a benchmark for handwritten character recognition.

Ba–Shu Dataset The Ba–Shu dataset was compiled from images sourced from the Sichuan Museum [31] and the Sanxingdui Museum [28], viewable in *Presentation and Translation of the Linguistic Landscape in the Sichuan Museum and the Spread of the Ba–Shu Culture from the Perspective of Cultural Communication* [38].

A.2 Packages Used

The complete implementation is available in the GitHub repository.

System and File Management

- [os](#), [shutil](#), [glob](#), [zipfile](#), [pathlib](#), [pickle](#)
For file operations, directory management, and handling archives.
- [logging](#), [warnings](#), [traceback](#), [datetime](#)
For system logging, error handling, and timestamping processes.

Data Science and Numerical Computing

- [numpy](#), [pandas](#)
For numerical operations, data manipulation, and tabular data processing.
- [seaborn](#), [matplotlib](#)
For data visualization and plotting.

Image Processing

- [Pillow \(PIL\)](#), [opencv-python \(cv2\)](#)
For image loading, preprocessing, and augmentation.
- [skimage](#)
For image filtering and additional processing.
- [fontTools](#)
For working with font files and glyph extraction.

Machine Learning and Deep Learning

- [torch](#), [torchvision](#)
For building and training neural networks on GPU.
- [timm](#), [transformers](#)
Pretrained models and advanced architectures for vision and NLP tasks.

Dimensionality Reduction and Clustering

- [sklearn.manifold.TSNE](#), [sklearn.decomposition.PCA](#)
For visualizing high-dimensional data.
- [KMeans](#), [cosine_similarity](#), [StandardScaler](#)
For unsupervised clustering and similarity analysis.

Evaluation Metrics and Analysis

- [confusion_matrix](#), [classification_report](#)
For evaluating model classification performance.

Hierarchical Clustering and Statistical Analysis

- [scipy.cluster.hierarchy](#), [scipy.spatial.distance](#)
For hierarchical clustering and distance computation.
- [scipy.stats.ttest_ind](#)
For statistical significance testing.

Graph Theory and Network Analysis

- [networkx](#)
For network-based graph analysis and visualization.

Web Scraping and Requests

- [requests](#), [BeautifulSoup \(bs4\)](#)
For accessing web resources and parsing HTML/XML data.

Progress Tracking and Utilities

- [tqdm](#)
For tracking progress of loops and operations.

Hardware Acceleration

- [torch.device\("cuda"\)](#)
For leveraging GPU acceleration when available.

All packages were installed using pip within the Colab environment. CUDA acceleration was used for deep learning tasks when available.

A.3 Ensemble t-SNE Visualizations

This subsection provides supplementary t-SNE projections for each target-trained embedding space (Indus-, Proto-Cuneiform-, and Proto-Elamite-trained ensembles). Each point corresponds to a single glyph image embedded using the corresponding ensemble feature extractor, and colors denote corpus identity. These plots are intended for qualitative visualization only (t-SNE preserves local neighborhoods but distorts global distances) and visually corroborate the clustering results summarized in Section 3.

Across all training regimes, several stable proximity patterns recur. Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite consistently occupy overlapping or adjacent regions within the same embedding spaces, while Modern Dongba forms a distinct, isolated cluster across projections. Indus, Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC), and Old Dongba typically appear grouped together and separated from the West Asian comparanda, though the compactness of this grouping varies by training space. In the Indus-trained embeddings, Indus lies closest to TYC and Old Dongba, whereas in the Proto-Cuneiform- and Proto-Elamite-trained spaces, Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite show the strongest mutual proximity. Despite differences in global layout and dispersion across models and random seeds, these relative relationships recur across projections, supporting the stability of the clustering structure observed in the full embedding space.

Figure 12: t-SNE projection of ensemble-averaged glyph embeddings in the Indus-trained feature space. Each point represents a glyph embedding and is colored by corpus. Indus occupies a region adjacent to Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC) and Old Dongba clusters, while Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform form separate groupings at greater distance; Modern Dongba appears as a distinct, more isolated cluster. Spatial relationships reflect relative proximity in the learned embedding space and are shown for visualization only.

Figure 13: Model-wise t-SNE projections for each of the five Indus-trained ensemble members (different random seeds), with the ensemble average shown at top left. Each point represents a glyph embedding and is colored by corpus. Despite variation in global layout across runs, similar relative groupings recur: Indus appears adjacent to TYC and Old Dongba, while Proto-Elamite, Proto-Cuneiform, and Modern Dongba occupy more separated regions. The recurrence of these relationships across seeds indicates that the observed structure is not driven by a single initialization.

Figure 14: t-SNE projection of ensemble-averaged glyph embeddings in the Proto-Cuneiform-trained feature space. Each point represents a glyph embedding and is colored by corpus. In this representation, Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite occupy overlapping or adjacent regions, while Indus, TYC, and Old Dongba form a more separated grouping and Modern Dongba appears as a distinct cluster. Spatial relationships reflect relative proximity in the learned embedding space and are shown for visualization only.

Figure 15: Model-wise t-SNE projections for each of the five Proto-Cuneiform-trained ensemble members (different random seeds), with the ensemble average shown at top left. Each point represents a glyph embedding and is colored by corpus. Although global layout varies across runs, similar relative groupings recur: Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite tend to occupy neighboring regions, while Indus, TYC, and Old Dongba appear in more distant regions and Modern Dongba forms a separate cluster. The recurrence of these relationships across seeds indicates that the observed structure is not driven by a single initialization.

Figure 16: t-SNE projection of ensemble-averaged glyph embeddings in the Proto-Elamite-trained feature space. Each point represents a glyph embedding and is colored by corpus. Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform occupy overlapping or adjacent regions, while Indus, TYC, and Old Dongba form a more separated grouping and Modern Dongba appears as a distinct cluster. Spatial relationships reflect relative proximity in the learned embedding space and are shown for visualization only.

Figure 17: Model-wise t-SNE projections for each of the five Proto-Elamite-trained ensemble members (different random seeds), with the ensemble average shown at top left. Each point represents a glyph embedding and is colored by corpus. Although global layout varies across runs, similar relative groupings recur: Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform tend to occupy neighboring regions, while Indus, TYC, and Old Dongba appear in a more distant grouping and Modern Dongba forms a separate cluster. The recurrence of these relationships across seeds indicates that the observed structure is not driven by a single initialization.

A.4 Ensemble PCA Visualization

This subsection provides supplementary PCA projections for each target-trained embedding space (Indus-, Proto-Cuneiform-, and Proto-Elamite-trained ensembles). Each point corresponds to a single glyph image embedded using the corresponding ensemble feature extractor, and colors denote corpus identity. PCA is a linear projection and is provided as a complementary view to the t-SNE plots in Appendix A.3, offering a visualization of dominant linear structure in the learned embedding spaces.

Across all training regimes, several consistent proximity patterns recur. Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite frequently occupy adjacent or overlapping regions within the same projections, while Modern Dongba forms a distinct, isolated cluster across embedding spaces. Indus, Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC), and Old Dongba typically appear grouped together and separated from the West Asian comparanda, though the compactness and orientation of this grouping vary by training space and by principal component axes. In the Indus-trained embeddings, Indus appears nearest to the TYC/Old Dongba grouping, whereas in the Proto-Cuneiform- and Proto-Elamite-trained spaces, Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite show the strongest mutual proximity. Despite differences in variance explained and global orientation across models and random seeds, these relative relationships recur across projections, supporting the stability of the clustering structure observed in the full embedding space.

Figure 18: PCA projection of ensemble-averaged glyph embeddings in the Indus-trained feature space. Each point represents a glyph embedding and is colored by corpus. Indus occupies a region adjacent to Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC) and Old Dongba, while Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite form a more separated grouping and Modern Dongba appears as a distinct cluster. Axes correspond to the first two principal components (PC1 = 16.80%, PC2 = 8.39%), and spatial relationships reflect relative proximity in the learned embedding space.

Indus - Ensemble 3D PCA Visualization
Total Explained Variance: 31.58%

Figure 19: 3D PCA projection of ensemble-averaged glyph embeddings in the Indus-trained feature space (PC1–PC3). Each point represents a glyph embedding and is colored by corpus. Indus forms a compact cluster separated from the West Asian comparanda, while Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC) and Old Dongba occupy an overlapping region on the negative-PC1 side (Old Dongba being a subset of the TYC dataset). Proto-Cuneiform and Modern Dongba lie in close proximity in this projection, with Proto-Elamite positioned nearby but offset primarily along PC3. The first three principal components together explain 31.58% of the variance (PC1 = 16.80%, PC2 = 8.39%, PC3 = 6.39%), and spatial relationships reflect relative proximity in the learned embedding space.

Figure 20: Model-wise PCA projections for each of the five Indus-trained ensemble members (different random seeds), with the ensemble average shown at top left. Each point represents a glyph embedding and is colored by corpus. While global orientation varies across runs, similar relative relationships recur: Indus appears adjacent to Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC) and Old Dongba, Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite occupy more distant regions, and Modern Dongba forms a separate cluster. The recurrence of these proximity patterns across seeds indicates that the observed structure is not driven by a single initialization.

Figure 21: PCA projection of ensemble-averaged glyph embeddings in the Proto-Cuneiform-trained feature space. Each point represents a glyph embedding and is colored by corpus. Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite occupy adjacent regions, while Indus, Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC), and Old Dongba form a more separated grouping; Modern Dongba appears as a distinct cluster. Axes correspond to the first two principal components (PC1 = 12.70%, PC2 = 5.03%), and spatial relationships reflect relative proximity in the learned embedding space.

Proto-Cuneiform - Ensemble 3D PCA Visualization
Total Explained Variance: 21.85%

Figure 22: 3D PCA projection of ensemble-averaged glyph embeddings in the Proto-Cuneiform-trained feature space (PC1–PC3). Each point represents a glyph embedding and is colored by corpus. Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite occupy closely neighboring regions, while Indus, Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC), and Old Dongba form a broader grouping at greater distance; Modern Dongba appears offset as a distinct cluster in the 3D projection. The first three principal components together explain 21.85% of the variance (PC1 = 12.70%, PC2 = 5.03%, PC3 = 4.12%), and spatial relationships reflect relative proximity in the learned embedding space.

Figure 23: Model-wise PCA projections for each of the five Proto-Cuneiform-trained ensemble members (different random seeds), with the ensemble average shown at top left. Each point represents a glyph embedding and is colored by corpus. Although global layout varies across runs, similar relative groupings recur: Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite tend to occupy neighboring regions, while Indus, Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC), and Old Dongba form a more distant grouping and Modern Dongba appears as a separate cluster. The recurrence of these relationships across seeds indicates that the observed structure is not driven by a single initialization.

Figure 24: PCA projection of ensemble-averaged glyph embeddings in the Proto-Elamite-trained feature space. Each point represents a glyph embedding and is colored by corpus. Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform occupy adjacent regions, while Indus, Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC), and Old Dongba form a separate grouping at greater distance; Modern Dongba appears as a distinct cluster. Axes correspond to the first two principal components (PC1 = 9.93%, PC2 = 6.80%), and spatial relationships reflect relative proximity in the learned embedding space.

Proto-Elamite - Ensemble 3D PCA Visualization
Total Explained Variance: 20.29%

Figure 25: 3D PCA projection of ensemble-averaged glyph embeddings in the Proto-Elamite-trained feature space (PC1–PC3). Each point represents a glyph embedding and is colored by corpus. Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform occupy neighboring regions, while Indus, Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC), and Old Dongba form a broader grouping at greater distance; Modern Dongba appears offset as a distinct cluster. The first three principal components together explain 20.29% of the variance (PC1 = 9.93%, PC2 = 6.80%, PC3 = 3.56%), and spatial relationships reflect relative proximity in the learned embedding space.

Figure 26: Model-wise PCA projections for each of the five Proto-Elamite-trained ensemble members (different random seeds), with the ensemble average shown at top left. Each point represents a glyph embedding and is colored by corpus. Despite variation in global orientation across runs, similar relative groupings recur: Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform tend to occupy neighboring regions, while Indus, Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC), and Old Dongba appear in a more distant grouping and Modern Dongba forms a separate cluster. The recurrence of these proximity patterns across seeds indicates that the observed structure is not driven by a single initialization.

A.5 Ensemble Hierarchical Clustering

This subsection provides supplementary dendrograms for the script-level hierarchical clustering analysis in each target-trained embedding space (Indus-, Proto-Cuneiform-, and Proto-Elamite-trained ensembles). Unless stated otherwise, clustering is performed on script-level (corpus-level) aggregated embeddings using cosine distance ($1 - \cos(\cdot, \cdot)$), where lower merge distance indicates greater similarity. Multiple linkage criteria are shown to assess structural stability: complete linkage merges clusters based on their farthest pairwise distance, average linkage uses the mean pairwise distance, Ward linkage minimizes within-cluster variance at each merge, and single linkage uses the nearest pairwise distance (and can produce chaining effects).

Across training regimes and linkage choices, several consistent structural patterns recur. Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite typically merge at the lowest distances within the same embedding spaces, while Tibetan–Yi Corridor (TYC) and Old Dongba form a neighboring cluster that often joins with Indus at intermediate distances. Modern Dongba consistently appears as the most distant branch across dendrograms. Although exact merge heights and ordering vary by linkage criterion and training space, these relative groupings remain broadly stable, indicating that the observed proximity structure is not driven by a single clustering configuration. As with the dimensionality reduction visualizations, these dendrograms provide a complementary qualitative view of relationships in the learned embedding spaces and should be interpreted alongside the quantitative analyses presented in Section 3.

Figure 27: Hierarchical clustering of script-level embeddings in the Indus-trained feature space using complete linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos(\cdot, \cdot)$). Lower merge heights indicate greater similarity. TYC and Old Dongba merge at the lowest distance, with Indus joining this cluster before merging with Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform. Modern Dongba remains the most distant branch. This configuration indicates that, under a conservative linkage criterion, Indus embeddings are more similar to the Tibetan–Yi Corridor grouping than to the West Asian comparanda.

Figure 28: Hierarchical clustering of script-level embeddings in the Indus-trained feature space using Ward linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos(\cdot, \cdot)$). Lower merge heights indicate greater similarity. TYC and Old Dongba again form the closest pair, with Indus merging with this grouping prior to Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform. Modern Dongba forms a separate branch at greater distance. The recurrence of this structure under variance-minimizing linkage supports the stability of the Indus–TYC–Old Dongba proximity.

Figure 29: Hierarchical clustering of script-level embeddings in the Indus-trained feature space using average linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos(\cdot, \cdot)$). Lower merge heights indicate greater visual-semantic similarity. TYC and Old Dongba merge first, followed by Indus, while Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform form a separate cluster at greater distance and Modern Dongba remains the most distant branch. Across linkage strategies, Indus consistently joins the Tibetan–Yi Corridor grouping prior to the West Asian scripts.

Figure 30: Hierarchical clustering of script-level embeddings in the Indus-trained feature space using single linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos(\cdot, \cdot)$). Lower merge heights indicate greater similarity. Although single linkage is sensitive to chaining effects, TYC and Old Dongba again merge first, with Indus joining this cluster before the Proto-Elamite-Proto-Cuneiform grouping and Modern Dongba merging last. The persistence of this ordering across linkage criteria indicates that the observed proximity is not driven by a specific clustering method.

Figure 31: Hierarchical clustering of script-level embeddings in the Proto-Cuneiform-trained feature space using complete linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos(\cdot, \cdot)$). Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform merge at the lowest distance, while TYC and Old Dongba form a neighboring cluster that joins with Indus at a higher merge height. Modern Dongba remains the most distant branch. This arrangement reflects strongest mutual similarity between the two West Asian corpora in this feature space.

Figure 32: Hierarchical clustering of script-level embeddings in the Proto-Cuneiform-trained feature space using Ward linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos(\cdot, \cdot)$). Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform again form the closest pair, while TYC and Old Dongba cluster together and merge with Indus prior to joining the West Asian cluster. Modern Dongba forms a separate branch. The recurrence of these relationships across linkage methods indicates stable grouping within this embedding space.

Figure 33: Hierarchical clustering of script-level embeddings in the Proto-Cuneiform-trained feature space using average linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos(\cdot, \cdot)$). Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform merge first, followed by a cluster comprising TYC and Old Dongba that subsequently joins with Indus. Modern Dongba merges at the greatest distance. This structure mirrors the pattern observed under other linkage criteria, indicating consistent relative proximities in the learned representation.

Figure 34: Hierarchical clustering of script-level embeddings in the Proto-Cuneiform-trained embedding space using single linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos(\cdot, \cdot)$). Lower merge distances indicate greater similarity. In this configuration, Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform merge at the lowest distance, while TYC and Old Dongba form a neighboring cluster that subsequently joins with Indus. Modern Dongba appears as a more distant branch. Although single linkage can produce chaining effects, the overall arrangement still separates the West Asian comparanda from the Indus-TYC-Old Dongba grouping.

Figure 35: Hierarchical clustering of script-level embeddings in the Proto-Elamite-trained embedding space using complete linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos(\cdot, \cdot)$). Lower merge distances indicate greater similarity. Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform cluster together at the lowest distances, while TYC and Old Dongba form a neighboring grouping that merges with Indus at a higher level. Modern Dongba forms a separate, more distant branch. This configuration mirrors patterns observed in other linkage criteria, with consistent separation between the West Asian pair and the Indus–TYC–Old Dongba grouping.

Figure 36: Hierarchical clustering of script-level embeddings in the Proto-Elamite-trained embedding space using Ward linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos(\cdot, \cdot)$). Lower merge distances indicate greater similarity. Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform again merge at the lowest level, while TYC and Old Dongba form a tight neighboring cluster that joins with Indus at a higher distance. Modern Dongba remains the most isolated branch. The recurrence of this structure under Ward linkage supports the stability of relationships observed across clustering methods.

Figure 37: Hierarchical clustering of script-level embeddings in the Proto-Elamite-trained embedding space using average linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos(\cdot, \cdot)$). Lower merge distances indicate greater similarity. TYC and Old Dongba form the closest pair, with Indus joining this grouping at an intermediate distance, while Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform cluster together separately. Modern Dongba appears as the most distant branch. This arrangement is consistent with the broader clustering structure observed across linkage criteria.

Figure 38: Hierarchical clustering of script-level embeddings in the Proto-Elamite-trained embedding space using single linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos(\cdot, \cdot)$). Lower merge distances indicate greater similarity. Proto-Elamite and Proto-Cuneiform merge at the lowest distance, while TYC and Old Dongba cluster together and subsequently join with Indus. Modern Dongba remains the most distant branch. Despite the sensitivity of single linkage to chaining, the same broad grouping relationships recur across linkage choices.

A.6 Clustering Heatmaps

This subsection presents clustered heatmaps of pairwise script-to-script cosine similarities within each target-trained embedding space (Indus-, Proto-Cuneiform-, and Proto-Elamite-trained ensembles). Each cell shows cosine similarity between corpus-level aggregated embeddings, with warmer colors indicating greater similarity. Rows and columns correspond to corpora; when clustering is applied, ordering follows the indicated linkage criterion (Ward, complete, average, or single) computed on cosine distance ($1 - \cos$). These visualizations complement the dendrograms by showing the magnitude and structure of inter-corpus similarities directly in matrix form.

Figure 39: Clustered heatmap of pairwise script-to-script cosine similarities in the Indus-trained embedding space. Rows/columns correspond to corpora; clustering uses Ward linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos$). Highest similarities occur between TYC and Old Dongba (≈ 0.97) and between Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite (≈ 0.93), while Indus shows stronger similarity to TYC and Old Dongba than to Proto-Elamite. Modern Dongba remains comparatively less similar to Old Dongba (≈ 0.82).

Figure 40: Clustered heatmap of pairwise script-to-script cosine similarities in the Indus-trained embedding space. Rows/columns correspond to corpora; clustering uses complete linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos$). The strongest affinities remain TYC–Old Dongba and Proto-Cuneiform–Proto-Elamite, with Indus positioned nearer the TYC/Old Dongba region than the West Asian pair. Modern Dongba continues to show lower similarity to Old Dongba than to Proto-Cuneiform.

Figure 41: Clustered heatmap of pairwise script-to-script cosine similarities in the Indus-trained embedding space. Rows/columns correspond to corpora; clustering uses average linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos$). The matrix again highlights two recurring similarity structures: a TYC/Old Dongba/Indus grouping and a Proto-Cuneiform/Proto-Elamite pairing. Indus maintains higher similarity to TYC than to Proto-Elamite, and Modern Dongba remains relatively distinct from Old Dongba.

Figure 42: Clustered heatmap of pairwise script-to-script cosine similarities in the Indus-trained embedding space. Rows/columns correspond to corpora; clustering uses single linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos$). Despite single linkage's tendency to chain nearby neighbors, the same strongest relationships persist: TYC–Old Dongba and Proto-Cuneiform–Proto-Elamite. Indus remains more similar to the TYC/Old Dongba pair than to Proto-Elamite, while Modern Dongba shows comparatively lower similarity to Old Dongba.

Figure 43: Clustered heatmap of pairwise script-to-script cosine similarities in the Proto-Cuneiform-trained embedding space. Rows/columns correspond to corpora; clustering uses Ward linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos$). A high-similarity block appears among TYC, Old Dongba, and Indus (≥ 0.96), while Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite form the strongest pair (≈ 0.98). Modern Dongba is more similar to Proto-Cuneiform than to Old Dongba, reinforcing its separation from the Old Dongba subset.

Figure 44: Clustered heatmap of pairwise script-to-script cosine similarities in the Proto-Cuneiform-trained embedding space. Rows/columns correspond to corpora; clustering uses complete linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos$). The strongest pairwise similarity remains Proto-Cuneiform–Proto-Elamite, while TYC and Old Dongba form a second high-similarity pair with Indus embedded nearby. Modern Dongba shows weaker similarity to Old Dongba than to Proto-Cuneiform.

Figure 45: Clustered heatmap of pairwise script-to-script cosine similarities in the Proto-Cuneiform-trained embedding space. Rows/columns correspond to corpora; clustering uses average linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos$). Two consistent structures remain visible: Proto-Cuneiform with Proto-Elamite, and TYC with Old Dongba and Indus. Indus maintains high similarity to TYC and Old Dongba (≈ 0.96 – 0.98) relative to its similarity with Proto-Elamite.

Figure 46: Clustered heatmap of pairwise script-to-script cosine similarities in the Proto-Cuneiform-trained embedding space. Rows/columns correspond to corpora; clustering uses single linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos$). The strongest similarities remain Proto-Cuneiform-Proto-Elamite and Old Dongba-TYC, with Indus closely aligned to the latter. Modern Dongba again shows lower similarity to Old Dongba than to Proto-Cuneiform.

Figure 47: Clustered heatmap of pairwise script-to-script cosine similarities in the Proto-Elamite-trained embedding space. Rows/columns correspond to corpora; clustering uses Ward linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos$). Old Dongba and TYC exhibit the highest similarity (≈ 0.98), with Indus closely aligned to this pair (≈ 0.96). Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite remain strongly paired (≈ 0.97), while Indus shows notably lower similarity to Modern Dongba (≈ 0.87).

Figure 48: Clustered heatmap of pairwise script-to-script cosine similarities in the Proto-Elamite-trained embedding space. Rows/columns correspond to corpora; clustering uses complete linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos$). The ordering again separates a TYC/Old Dongba/Indus region from the Proto-Cuneiform/Proto-Elamite pair. Indus remains most similar to TYC and Old Dongba and least similar to Modern Dongba.

Figure 49: Clustered heatmap of pairwise script-to-script cosine similarities in the Proto-Elamite-trained embedding space. Rows/columns correspond to corpora; clustering uses average linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos$). The highest similarities occur between Old Dongba and TYC and between Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite. Indus remains embedded within the TYC/Old Dongba similarity region, while Modern Dongba shows lower similarity to Indus than to Proto-Cuneiform.

Figure 50: Clustered heatmap of pairwise script-to-script cosine similarities in the Proto-Elamite-trained embedding space. Rows/columns correspond to corpora; clustering uses single linkage on cosine distance ($1 - \cos$). Even under single linkage, the strongest affinities remain Old Dongba–TYC and Proto-Cuneiform–Proto-Elamite. Indus remains closer to the TYC/Old Dongba group than to Modern Dongba.

A.7 Cosine Similarity Plots

This subsection presents script-to-script cosine similarity estimates computed within each target-trained embedding space (Indus-, Proto-Cuneiform-, and Proto-Elamite-trained ensembles). For each plot, the target corpus is embedded using its corresponding ensemble feature extractor and compared to all other corpora in the same feature space. Points represent ensemble-averaged cosine similarity values, and error bars denote standard deviation across random-seed ensemble members.

Across training regimes, several consistent patterns recur. Similarities within the Tibetan–Yi Corridor grouping (TYC and Old Dongba) remain high across spaces, reflecting their shared corpus structure. Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite show strong mutual similarity within West Asian-trained spaces, while Modern Dongba typically appears more isolated. Indus exhibits its highest similarity to TYC (and often Old Dongba) in the Indus-trained space, whereas in West Asian-trained spaces it shows comparatively weaker proximity to Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite. These relative relationships remain stable across ensemble seeds, as indicated by modest variance in most comparisons.

Figure 51: Script-to-script cosine similarities in the Indus-trained embedding space (Indus ensemble used as the feature extractor). TYC shows the highest similarity to Indus aside from the identity baseline, followed by Proto-Cuneiform and Old Dongba. Proto-Elamite and Modern Dongba exhibit lower similarity values. Error bars indicate standard deviation across ensemble seeds.

Figure 52: Script-to-script cosine similarities in the Proto-Cuneiform-trained embedding space. Proto-Elamite shows the strongest similarity to Proto-Cuneiform, followed by Modern Dongba and TYC. Indus appears moderately similar, while Old Dongba shows greater variance across ensemble members. Error bars indicate standard deviation across seeds.

Figure 53: Script-to-script cosine similarities in the Proto-Elamite-trained embedding space. Proto-Cuneiform exhibits the highest similarity to Proto-Elamite, followed by TYC. Old Dongba and Modern Dongba occupy intermediate ranges, while Indus shows comparatively lower similarity to Proto-Elamite. Error bars indicate standard deviation across ensemble seeds.

A.8 Grad-CAM Visualizations

This subsection presents representative Grad-CAM visualizations for selected glyphs across the Indus, Proto-Cuneiform, Proto-Elamite, and Dongba corpora. Grad-CAM highlights regions of each input image that contribute most strongly to the learned embedding representation. Warmer colors indicate higher contribution, while cooler colors indicate lower contribution. These visualizations provide qualitative evidence that the embedding model attends to structurally meaningful components of glyphs, such as stroke intersections, internal markings, and compositional features, rather than background regions.

Only CNN-based Grad-CAM visualizations are shown. Although the ensemble model also includes a Swin Transformer pathway, patch-based transformer architectures produce attribution maps at the token/window level that do not reliably project to fine-grained pixel-space explanations for these small glyph images. In preliminary experiments, Swin attributions appeared as coarse or grid-like patterns that were difficult to interpret spatially. For clarity and interpretability, only the CNN Grad-CAM overlays are presented here, which provide more stable and visually meaningful localization. Examples are selected for clarity and are intended as illustrative rather than exhaustive.

Indus Script

Figure 54: Representative Grad-CAM visualization for an Indus glyph (ID 142). Heatmaps indicate regions contributing most strongly to the learned representation (warmer colors = higher contribution).

Figure 55: Representative Grad-CAM visualization for an Indus glyph (ID 874). Heatmaps indicate regions contributing most strongly to the learned representation (warmer colors = higher contribution).

Proto-Cuneiform

Figure 56: Representative Grad-CAM visualization for a Proto-Cuneiform glyph (1N52). Heatmaps indicate regions contributing most strongly to the learned representation (warmer colors = higher contribution).

Figure 57: Representative Grad-CAM visualization for a Proto-Cuneiform glyph (MUNSZUBb). Heatmaps indicate regions contributing most strongly to the learned representation (warmer colors = higher contribution).

Proto-Elamite

Figure 58: Representative Grad-CAM visualization for a Proto-Elamite glyph (M201+M377). Heatmaps indicate regions contributing most strongly to the learned representation (warmer colors = higher contribution).

Figure 59: Representative Grad-CAM visualization for a Proto-Elamite glyph (M304-A). Heatmaps indicate regions contributing most strongly to the learned representation (warmer colors = higher contribution).

Modern Dongba

Figure 60: Representative Grad-CAM visualization for a Modern Dongba glyph (E4C8). Heatmaps indicate regions contributing most strongly to the learned representation (warmer colors = higher contribution).

Figure 61: Representative Grad-CAM visualization for a Modern Dongba glyph (E62A). Heatmaps indicate regions contributing most strongly to the learned representation (warmer colors = higher contribution).

Old Dongba

Figure 62: Representative Grad-CAM visualization for an Old Dongba glyph (class 61). Heatmaps indicate regions contributing most strongly to the learned representation (warmer colors = higher contribution).

Figure 63: Representative Grad-CAM visualization for an Old Dongba glyph (class 29). Heatmaps indicate regions contributing most strongly to the learned representation (warmer colors = higher contribution).

A.9 Field photographs: Tibetan rock art

This subsection presents field photographs of pre-Buddhist rock art documented at Namucuo, Tibet, during site visits conducted following recommendations from John Vincent Belleza. These images are included as contextual visual material referenced in the discussion. They illustrate broader pictographic and geometric traditions present across the Tibetan Plateau prior to the spread of Buddhism and provide qualitative motivation for exploring cross-regional similarities in symbolic form. The photographs are presented for contextual reference only and are not intended as direct evidence of transmission or lineage.

Figure 64: Field photograph of pre-Buddhist rock art at Namucuo, Tibet. The panel contains linear anthropomorphic and geometric motifs characteristic of early Tibetan Plateau pictographic traditions. Photograph by the author (2024).

Figure 65: Rock art panel from Namucuo, Tibet, showing layered mineral pigments and weathered pictographic forms. Such motifs provide contextual visual reference for the broader symbolic environments discussed in Section 4. Photograph by the author (2024).

A.10 Statistical Tests

This subsection reports pairwise statistical comparisons of script-level cosine similarity distributions within each target-trained embedding space. For each ensemble model, glyph embeddings were aggregated by script and compared using two-sample t-tests to evaluate whether similarities to the Indus script differed from similarities to Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite.

Cohen's d is reported to quantify the magnitude of these differences across ensemble seeds.

Across models, Tibetan–Yi Corridor, Modern Dongba, and Old Dongba corpora show consistently higher similarity to the Indus script than to the Bronze Age Proto-Cuneiform or Proto-Elamite corpora, with predominantly large effect sizes. These results complement the clustering and similarity analyses presented in the main text, supporting the observation that Tibetan–Yi systems occupy a closer position to Indus within the learned visual embedding spaces. Full test outputs are provided for transparency.

Table 6: Pairwise two-sample t-tests comparing script-level cosine similarity distributions across ensemble models. For each comparison script, similarities to the Indus script are contrasted with similarities to Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite. Reported values include mean similarities, test statistics, p -values, and Cohen’s d effect sizes. Across models, Tibetan–Yi Corridor corpora exhibit consistently higher similarity to Indus than to the West Asian Bronze Age signaries, with large effect sizes in most comparisons.

Comparison Script	Model	Test	Mean 1	Mean 2	Difference	T-statistic	P-value	Cohen’s d	Effect Size	Significant	Better Match
TYC	model_0	Indus_vs_Proto-Cuneiform	0.61	0.07	0.54	3430.39	0.00	9.70	large	Yes	Indus
TYC	model_0	Indus_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.61	0.10	0.51	3143.15	0.00	8.89	large	Yes	Indus
TYC	model_0	Proto-Cuneiform_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.07	0.10	-0.03	-412.76	0.00	-1.17	large	Yes	Proto-Elamite
TYC	model_1	Indus_vs_Proto-Cuneiform	0.61	0.07	0.54	2362.56	0.00	6.68	large	Yes	Indus
TYC	model_1	Indus_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.61	0.07	0.54	2328.76	0.00	6.59	large	Yes	Indus
TYC	model_1	Proto-Cuneiform_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.07	0.07	0.00	1.77	0.08	0.01	negligible	No	Proto-Cuneiform
TYC	model_2	Indus_vs_Proto-Cuneiform	0.63	0.07	0.56	2720.97	0.00	7.70	large	Yes	Indus
TYC	model_2	Indus_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.63	0.08	0.55	2696.50	0.00	7.63	large	Yes	Indus
TYC	model_2	Proto-Cuneiform_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.07	0.08	-0.01	-117.34	0.00	-0.33	small	Yes	Proto-Elamite
TYC	model_3	Indus_vs_Proto-Cuneiform	0.65	0.07	0.58	2331.90	0.00	6.60	large	Yes	Indus
TYC	model_3	Indus_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.65	0.07	0.58	2385.25	0.00	6.75	large	Yes	Indus
TYC	model_3	Proto-Cuneiform_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.07	0.07	0.00	4.93	0.00	0.01	negligible	Yes	Proto-Cuneiform
TYC	model_4	Indus_vs_Proto-Cuneiform	0.67	0.23	0.44	1868.95	0.00	5.29	large	Yes	Indus
TYC	model_4	Indus_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.66	0.07	0.59	2670.99	0.00	7.55	large	Yes	Indus
TYC	model_4	Proto-Cuneiform_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.23	0.07	0.16	1391.71	0.00	3.94	large	Yes	Proto-Cuneiform
Modern Dongba	model_0	Indus_vs_Proto-Cuneiform	0.58	0.07	0.51	3428.45	0.00	9.70	large	Yes	Indus
Modern Dongba	model_0	Indus_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.58	0.08	0.50	3406.41	0.00	9.63	large	Yes	Indus
Modern Dongba	model_0	Proto-Cuneiform_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.07	0.08	-0.01	-145.12	0.00	-0.41	small	Yes	Proto-Elamite
Modern Dongba	model_1	Indus_vs_Proto-Cuneiform	0.65	0.05	0.60	3414.21	0.00	9.66	large	Yes	Indus
Modern Dongba	model_1	Indus_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.66	0.10	0.56	3329.02	0.00	9.42	large	Yes	Indus
Modern Dongba	model_1	Proto-Cuneiform_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.06	0.10	-0.04	-523.73	0.00	-1.48	large	Yes	Proto-Elamite
Modern Dongba	model_2	Indus_vs_Proto-Cuneiform	0.58	0.05	0.53	2773.65	0.00	7.85	large	Yes	Indus
Modern Dongba	model_2	Indus_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.58	0.10	0.48	2461.76	0.00	6.96	large	Yes	Indus
Modern Dongba	model_2	Proto-Cuneiform_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.05	0.09	-0.04	-483.31	0.00	-1.37	large	Yes	Proto-Elamite
Modern Dongba	model_3	Indus_vs_Proto-Cuneiform	0.68	0.08	0.60	2883.93	0.00	8.16	large	Yes	Indus
Modern Dongba	model_3	Indus_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.68	0.08	0.60	3069.56	0.00	8.68	large	Yes	Indus
Modern Dongba	model_3	Proto-Cuneiform_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.08	0.08	0.00	59.78	0.00	0.17	negligible	Yes	Proto-Cuneiform
Modern Dongba	model_4	Indus_vs_Proto-Cuneiform	0.68	0.28	0.40	1672.96	0.00	4.73	large	Yes	Indus
Modern Dongba	model_4	Indus_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.68	0.08	0.59	2651.29	0.00	7.50	large	Yes	Indus
Modern Dongba	model_4	Proto-Cuneiform_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.28	0.08	0.20	1789.15	0.00	5.06	large	Yes	Proto-Cuneiform
Old Dongba	model_0	Indus_vs_Proto-Cuneiform	0.62	0.07	0.55	3605.37	0.00	10.20	large	Yes	Indus
Old Dongba	model_0	Indus_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.62	0.10	0.52	3376.88	0.00	9.55	large	Yes	Indus
Old Dongba	model_0	Proto-Cuneiform_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.07	0.10	-0.03	-400.45	0.00	-1.13	large	Yes	Proto-Elamite
Old Dongba	model_1	Indus_vs_Proto-Cuneiform	0.58	0.08	0.50	2096.98	0.00	5.93	large	Yes	Indus
Old Dongba	model_1	Indus_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.58	0.05	0.53	2358.66	0.00	6.67	large	Yes	Indus
Old Dongba	model_1	Proto-Cuneiform_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.07	0.05	0.02	263.14	0.00	0.74	medium	Yes	Proto-Cuneiform
Old Dongba	model_2	Indus_vs_Proto-Cuneiform	0.66	0.08	0.58	3075.61	0.00	8.70	large	Yes	Indus

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Table 6 Continued from previous page

Comparison Script	Model	Test	Mean 1	Mean 2	Difference	T-statistic	P-value	Cohen's d	Effect Size	Significant	Better Match
Old Dongba	model_2	Indus_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.66	0.09	0.57	2944.56	0.00	8.33	large	Yes	Indus
Old Dongba	model_2	Proto-Cuneiform_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.07	0.08	-0.01	-118.30	0.00	-0.33	small	Yes	Proto-Elamite
Old Dongba	model_3	Indus_vs_Proto-Cuneiform	0.61	0.08	0.52	2145.70	0.00	6.07	large	Yes	Indus
Old Dongba	model_3	Indus_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.59	0.07	0.52	2082.42	0.00	5.89	large	Yes	Indus
Old Dongba	model_3	Proto-Cuneiform_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.08	0.07	0.01	202.07	0.00	0.57	medium	Yes	Proto-Cuneiform
Old Dongba	model_4	Indus_vs_Proto-Cuneiform	0.65	0.22	0.42	1745.20	0.00	4.94	large	Yes	Indus
Old Dongba	model_4	Indus_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.65	0.07	0.58	2550.84	0.00	7.21	large	Yes	Indus
Old Dongba	model_4	Proto-Cuneiform_vs_Proto-Elamite	0.22	0.07	0.16	1430.05	0.00	4.04	large	Yes	Proto-Cuneiform

A.11 Similarity Summary

This appendix aggregates mean script-to-script cosine similarities across ensemble models within each target-trained embedding space. Means, standard deviations, and 95% confidence intervals are computed across seeds. These values provide a complementary view to the statistical tests and clustering analyses in the main text, illustrating relative proximity between scripts in the learned visual embedding spaces. In the Indus-trained space, Tibetan–Yi Corridor corpora show the highest average similarity to Indus, followed by Old Dongba and Modern Dongba, while Proto-Cuneiform and Proto-Elamite show comparatively lower similarity. These patterns align with clustering and dimensionality reduction results presented in the main analysis.

Table 7: Aggregate cosine similarities to Indus in the Indus-trained embedding space. Values are means \pm standard deviations across ensemble models, with 95% confidence intervals.

Script	Mean Similarity	Std Dev	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
Indus	1.0000	0.0000	1.0000	1.0000
TYC	0.9297	0.0145	0.9170	0.9424
Proto-Cuneiform	0.8873	0.0272	0.8634	0.9111
Old Dongba	0.8777	0.0560	0.8287	0.9268
Proto-Elamite	0.8550	0.0420	0.8182	0.8918
Modern Dongba	0.8518	0.0179	0.8361	0.8675

Table 8: Aggregate cosine similarities to Proto-Cuneiform in the Proto-Cuneiform-trained embedding space. Values are means \pm standard deviations across ensemble models, with 95% confidence intervals.

Script	Mean Similarity	Std Dev	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
Proto-Cuneiform	1.0000	0.0000	1.0000	1.0000
Proto-Elamite	0.9860	0.0067	0.9801	0.9919
Modern Dongba	0.9500	0.0177	0.9345	0.9655
TYC	0.9463	0.0300	0.9199	0.9726
Indus	0.9115	0.0201	0.8939	0.9292
Old Dongba	0.8828	0.0821	0.8109	0.9548

Table 9: Aggregate cosine similarities to Proto-Elamite in the Proto-Elamite-trained embedding space. Values are means \pm standard deviations across ensemble models, with 95% confidence intervals.

Script	Mean Similarity	Std Dev	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
Proto-Elamite	1.0000	0.0000	1.0000	1.0000
Proto-Cuneiform	0.9726	0.0144	0.9600	0.9852
TYC	0.9450	0.0173	0.9298	0.9601
Old Dongba	0.9130	0.0276	0.8888	0.9372
Modern Dongba	0.9127	0.0252	0.8906	0.9347
Indus	0.9088	0.0182	0.8928	0.9247

A.12 Model Training Data

This subsection provides training summaries for the hybrid convolutional-transformer ensembles used throughout the study. For each target script (Indus, Proto-Cuneiform, Proto-Elamite), five independently initialized models were trained with identical architectures and data splits.

Validation loss trajectories and learning-rate schedules are included to demonstrate stable convergence across seeds and to verify that cross-script similarity results are not driven by single-run artifacts. The consistency of validation behavior across ensemble members supports the robustness of the embedding spaces used in the comparative analyses presented in the main text.

Table 10: Indus training summary for ensemble feature extractors. Each model was trained independently with identical architecture and data splits. Reported validation losses correspond to the best checkpoint for each seed.

model_idx	seed	val_loss	epoch	model_path
1	42	9.65621223449707	3	Indus_ensemble_1_hybrid_extractor_best.pth
2	43	9.49264907836914	1	Indus_ensemble_2_hybrid_extractor_best.pth
3	44	9.3032808303833	11	Indus_ensemble_3_hybrid_extractor_best.pth
4	45	9.921699905395508	1	Indus_ensemble_4_hybrid_extractor_best.pth
5	46	10.057604217529297	1	Indus_ensemble_5_hybrid_extractor_best.pth

Interpretation Across seeds, validation losses fall within a narrow range, indicating stable convergence and no outlier runs. This consistency suggests that the learned Indus embedding space is not dependent on a single initialization and supports the use of an ensemble representation in the cross-script similarity analysis presented in the main text.

Figure 66: Training and validation loss curves (left) and learning-rate schedules (right) for the five Indus ensemble models. Convergence behavior is consistent across seeds, indicating stable feature learning within the Indus embedding space used for cross-script comparison.

Table 11: Proto-Cuneiform training summary for ensemble feature extractors. Each model was trained independently with identical architecture and data splits. Reported validation losses correspond to the best checkpoint for each seed.

model_idx	seed	val_loss	epoch	model_path
1	42	8.801242896488734	11	Proto-Cuneiform_ensemble_1_hybrid_extractor_best.pth
2	43	8.71736410685948	11	Proto-Cuneiform_ensemble_2_hybrid_extractor_best.pth
3	44	8.819251537322998	7	Proto-Cuneiform_ensemble_3_hybrid_extractor_best.pth
4	45	8.773778438568115	9	Proto-Cuneiform_ensemble_4_hybrid_extractor_best.pth
5	46	9.27264860698155	1	Proto-Cuneiform_ensemble_5_hybrid_extractor_best.pth

Interpretation Validation losses are tightly clustered across seeds, with no evidence of unstable or divergent runs. The similarity of loss trajectories and learning-rate schedules supports a robust Proto-Cuneiform embedding space, reducing the likelihood that cross-script comparisons are driven by an anomalous training instance.

Figure 67: Training and validation loss curves (left) and learning-rate schedules (right) for the five Proto-Cuneiform ensemble models. Convergence patterns are consistent across seeds, supporting the stability of the Proto-Cuneiform embedding space used in cross-script similarity analyses.

Table 12: Proto-Elamite training summary for ensemble feature extractors. Each model was trained independently with identical architecture and data splits. Reported validation losses correspond to the best checkpoint for each seed.

model_idx	seed	val_loss	epoch	model_path
1	42	9.465515518188477	13	Proto-Elamite_ensemble_1_hybrid_extractor_best.pth
2	43	10.229036331176758	5	Proto-Elamite_ensemble_2_hybrid_extractor_best.pth
3	44	9.9594895362854	1	Proto-Elamite_ensemble_3_hybrid_extractor_best.pth
4	45	9.304905700683594	12	Proto-Elamite_ensemble_4_hybrid_extractor_best.pth
5	46	9.408125591278075	11	Proto-Elamite_ensemble_5_hybrid_extractor_best.pth

Interpretation Although the best validation losses vary modestly across seeds, all runs exhibit clear convergence and comparable schedule dynamics. The absence of qualitatively distinct outliers supports treating the Proto-Elamite embedding space as stable at the ensemble level, which is essential when contrasting Proto-Elamite similarities against Indus and Tibetan–Yi Corridor corpora.

Figure 68: Training and validation loss curves (left) and learning-rate schedules (right) for the five Proto-Elamite ensemble models. All seeds converge with broadly similar dynamics, supporting a robust Proto-Elamite embedding space for cross-script comparisons.

A.13 Architectural Equations

This appendix collects standard formulations referenced by the architectural description in Section 2.3. These equations describe well-established components (residual mappings, scaled dot-product attention, and a two-layer projection head) and are reproduced here for completeness; they are not study-specific.

Residual block (CNN pathway) The ResNet-18 encoder applies stacked residual blocks of the form [15]

$$y = \mathcal{F}(x, \{W_i\}) + x, \quad (4)$$

where \mathcal{F} denotes the residual mapping learned by the convolutional layers within the block, and the additive identity shortcut preserves gradient flow during training.

Scaled dot-product attention (Transformer pathway) The attention operation in the Swin Transformer pathway follows the standard formulation [33]:

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{SoftMax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V, \quad (5)$$

where Q , K , and V denote query, key, and value matrices and d_k is the key dimensionality. The Swin variant restricts this operation to shifted local windows [21].

Projection head (feature fusion) The fused 1536-dimensional representation is projected to the final 256-dimensional embedding via a two-layer MLP with batch normalization, ReLU activation, and dropout:

$$g = \text{BN}(W_2 \text{ReLU}(\text{BN}(W_1 z + b_1)) + b_2), \quad (6)$$

where $z \in \mathbb{R}^{1536}$ is the concatenated CNN-Transformer feature vector and W_1 , W_2 , b_1 , b_2 are learned parameters of the projection layers.